

ISSN (p): 3030-3362

№ 5 (27)

27.05.2025

IF 2024
11.7

RTADQIQ VA TATBIQ

Research and implementation
scientific-methodical journal

S C I E N C E S

Exact, Natural, Political, Social, Economic, Technical, Medical, Pedagogical

Editor in Chief:

F.M.Mukhtarov
PhD, associate prof

Executive editor

S.I.Zokirov
PhD, associate prof

Languages:

Uzbek, Russian, English and
Karakalpak

Registered in the Agency of
Information and Mass
Communications under the
Administration of the
President of the Republic of
Uzbekistan on May 3, 2023
under number 078777.

[IF-2024: 11.7](#)

@ferteach_uz

+99893-343-13-14

<https://rai-journal.uz>

Editorial Board:

B.R.Ismailov – Dr. Tech. Sc., Prof., M.Avezov South Kaz. Univ., Shymkent, Kazakhstan
I.Bjorn - Ph.D., Imeritus, Technical University of Denmark, Copenhagen, Denmark
A.Rasulov – Dr. Phys.-Math. Sc., Prof., TUIT Fergana Branch, Fergana, Uzbekistan
L.K.Mamadaliyeva – Dr. Tech. Sc. (DSc), Prof., FerPI, Fergana, Uzbekistan
M.E.Yunusaliyev – Dr. Tech. Sc. (DSc), Prof., FerPI, Fergana, Uzbekistan
X.B.Ismailov – Can. Tech. Sc., Assoc. Prof., M.Avezov South Kaz. Univ., Shymkent, Kazakhstan
J.T.Moldaliyev – Can. Bio. Sc., Assoc. Prof., OshSU, Osh, Kyrgyzstan
O.S.Nazarmatov – DSc in Econ., TUIT Fergana Branch, Fergana, Uzbekistan
G.K.Obidova - DSc in Ped., TUIT Fergana Branch, Fergana, Uzbekistan
T.M.Abdullayev - Ph.D. in Tech. Sc., TUIT Fergana Branch, Fergana, Uzbekistan.
N.I.Ibrokhimov - Ph.D. in Phys.-Math., TUIT Fergana Branch, Fergana, Uzbekistan.
A.R.Nurmatov - Ph.D. in History, NamSU, Fergana, Uzbekistan.
T.Yu.Bakirov - PhD in Ped. Sc., FarSU, Fergana, Uzbekistan
D.F.Tukhtasinov - Ph.D. in Ped. Sc., TUIT Fergana branch, Fergana, Uzbekistan.
S.B.Atajonova - Ph.D in Ped. Sc., AndMI, Andijan Uzbekistan
Sh.A.Umarov - Ph.D. in Phys.-Math. Sc., TUIT Fergana branch, Fergana, Uzbekistan.
I.A.Rustamov - Ph.D. in Phil. Sc., TUIT Fergana branch, Fergana, Uzbekistan.
B.Kh.Tolipov - Ph.D. in Phil. Sc., TUIT Fergana branch, Fergana, Uzbekistan.
O.Kh.Otakulov - Can. Tech. Sc., Assoc. Prof., TUIT Fergana branch, Uzbekistan
O.S.Raimjonova - Ph.D in Tech. Sc., Assoc. Prof., TUIT Fergana branch, Uzbekistan
R.A.Nurdinova - Ph.D in Tech. Sc., Assoc. Prof., TUIT Fergana branch, Uzbekistan
M.I.Ismoilov - Ph.D in Tech. Sc., Assoc. Prof., TUIT Fergana branch, Uzbekistan
I.T.Tojiboyev - Can. Tech. Sc., Assoc. Prof., Fergana State University, Uzbekistan
Sh.J.Kholmatov - Ph.D., TUIT Fergana branch, Fergana, Uzbekistan
Z.N.Khatamova - Ph.D. in Tech. Sc., TUIT Fergana branch, Fergana, Uzbekistan
Q.Kh. Akhunov - Can. Tech. Sc., Assoc. Prof., Fergana Polytechnic Institute, Uzbekistan
M.Kh. Okhunov - Can. Tech. Sc., Assoc. Prof., Fergana Polytechnic Institute, Uzbekistan
A.Q. Khomidov - Can. Tech. Sc., Assoc. Prof., Fergana Polytechnic Institute, Uzbekistan
Sh.Sh. Akramov - PhD, TUIT Fergana Branch, Fergana, Uzbekistan
A.A. Salimov - PhD in Econ., Fergana Polytechnic Institute, Uzbekistan
Z.G'. Ubaydullayev – Can. Econ., TUIT Qarchi Branch, Qarchi, Uzbekistan
S.S. Ibragimov - Ph.D in Tech. Sc., AndMI, Andijan Uzbekistan
Sh.J. Kholmatov - Ph.D. in Phil., TUIT Fergana Branch, Fergana, Uzbekistan
G.D. Kuchkarova - Ph.D. in Phil., TUIT Fergana Branch, Fergana, Uzbekistan
I.R.Teshabayeva - Ph.D. in Tech. Sc., TUIT Fergana Branch, Fergana, Uzbekistan
A.L.Meliqzhiyev - Ph.D. in Phil. Sc., TUIT Fergana Branch, Fergana, Uzbekistan
O.U.Kholmatova - Ph.D. in Phil. Sc., TUIT Fergana Branch, Fergana, Uzbekistan
N.N.Radjabov - Ph.D. in Phil. Sc., Assoc. Prof., Oriental University, Tashkent, Uzbekistan
Sh.A.Yuldashov - Ph.D. in Tech. Sc., Fergana State University, Fergana, Uzbekistan
A.A.Yuldashev - Ph.D. in Tech. Sc., Fergana State University, Fergana, Uzbekistan
M.Israilov - Can. Tech. Sc., Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan Academy of Forces
N.S.Abdullaeva - PhD in Ped. Sc., NamDU, Namangan, Uzbekistan
A.G.Turgunboyeva - PhD in Ped. Sc., NamDPI, Namangan, Uzbekistan
M.A.Abdullaeva - Prof., NamDU, Namangan, Uzbekistan
I.O.Ergashev - PhD in Econ., Fiscal Institute, Tashkent, Uzbekistan
N.T.Mamatxanova - PhD in Ped. Sc., NamDPI, Namangan, Uzbekistan
U.Yu.Akhundzhanov - PhD in Tech. Sc., TUIT Fergana Branch, Fergana, Uzbekistan
O.M.Ergashev - PhD in Tech. Sc., TUIT Fergana Branch, Fergana, Uzbekistan
N.R.Khallieva - PhD in Econ., Bukhara MTI, Bukhara, Uzbekistan
F.K.Achilova – Can. Econ. Sc., TUIT Qarchi Branch, Qarchi, Uzbekistan
A.K.Samyayev - PhD in Geog., Sam. Reg. Ped. Skills Center, Samarkand, Uzbekistan
J.S.Abdullayev - Can. Phys.-Math. Sc., Assoc. Prof., TUIT Fergana branch, Uzbekistan
N.D.Botirova –PhD in Ped, TUIT Fergana Branch, Fergana, Uzbekistan

Bosh muharrir:

F.M.Mukhtarov
PhD, dotsent

Ijrochi muharrir:

S.I.Zokirov
PhD, dotsent

Nashr tillari:

O'zbek, Rus, Inzliz va
Qoraqalpoq

O'zbekiston Respublikasi
Prezidenti Administratsiyasi
huzuridagi Axborot va
ommaviy
kommunikatsiyalar agentligi
tomonidan 2023-yil
3-mayda 078777 raqami
bilan ro'yxatga olingan.

IF-2024: 11.7

 [@feriteach_uz](https://t.me/feriteach_uz)
 +99893-343-13-14
 <https://rai-journal.uz>

Tahrir hay'ati:

B.R.Ismailov – t.f.d., prof. M.Avezov Jan. Qoz. Univ-ti., Chimkent, Qozog'iston
I.Byorno – Ph.D., Imeritus, Daniya Texnika Universiteti, Kopengagen, Daniya
A.Rasulov – f.-m.f.d., prof. TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston
L.K.Mamadaliyeva – t.f.d. (DSc), prof. FarPI, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston
M.E.Yunusaliyev – t.f.d. (DSc), prof. FarPI, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston
X.B.Ismailov – t.f.n., dot., M.Avezov Jan. Qoz. Univ-ti., Chimkent, Qozog'iston
J.T.Moldaliyev – bio. f. n., dotsent. OshDU, Osh, Qirg'iziston
O.S.Nazarmatov – iqt.f.d. DSc, TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston
G.K.Obidova – ped.f.d. DSc, TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston
T.M.Abdullayev – t.f.b. Ph.D., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.
N.I.Ibrokhimov – f.-m.f.b. Ph.D., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.
A.R.Nurmatov – tarix f.b. Ph.D., NamDU, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.
T.Yu.Bakirov – ped. f.b. PhD, FarDU, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston
D.F.To'xtasinov – ped.f.b. Ph.D., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.
S.B.Atajonova – ped.f.b. Ph.D, AndMI, Andijon O'zbekiston
Sh.A.Umarov – f.-m.f.b. Ph.D., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.
I.A.Rustamov – fal.f.b. Ph.D., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.
B.X.Tolipov – ff.b. Ph.D., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.
O.X.Otaqulov – t.f.n., dotsent. TATU Farg'ona filiali, O'zbekiston
O.S.Raimjonova – t.f.b. Ph.D, dotsent, TATU Farg'ona filiali, O'zbekiston
R.A.Nurdinova – t.f.b. Ph.D, dotsent, TATU Farg'ona filiali, O'zbekiston
M.I.Ismoilov – t.f.b. Ph.D, dotsent, TATU Farg'ona filiali, O'zbekiston
I.T.Tojiboyev – t.f.n., dotsent, Farg'ona davlat universiteti, O'zbekiston
Sh.J.Kholmatov – i.i.f.b. PhD., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston
Z.N.Khatamova – t.f.b. PhD., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston
Q.X. Axunov – t.f.n., dotsent, Farg'ona politexnika instituti, O'zbekiston
M.X. Oxunov – t.f.n., dotsent, Farg'ona politexnika instituti, O'zbekiston
A.Q.Xomidov – t.f.n., dotsent, Farg'ona politexnika instituti, O'zbekiston
Sh.Sh.Akramov – q.x.f.b. PhD, TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston
A.A.Salimov – iqt.f.b. PhD, Farg'ona politexnika instituti, O'zbekiston
Z.G'.Ubaydullayev – iqt.f.n., TATU Qarchi filiali, Qarchi, O'zbekiston
S.S.Ibragimov – t.f.b. Ph.D, AndMI, Andijon O'zbekiston
Sh.J.Xolmatov – fal.f.b. Ph.D., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston
G.D.Kuchkarova – fal.f.b. Ph.D., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston
I.R.Teshabayeva – t.f.b. Ph.D., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston
A.L.Meliquziyev – fil.f.b. Ph.D., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston
O.U.Xolmatova – fil.f.b. Ph.D., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston
N.N.Radjabov – fil.f.b. Ph.D., dotsent, Oriental University, Toshkent, O'zbekiston
Sh.A.Yuldashov – t.f.b. Ph.D., Farg'ona davlat universiteti, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston
A.A.Yuldashev – t.f.b. Ph.D., Farg'ona davlat universiteti, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston
M.Israilov – t.f.n., O'zbekiston Respublikasi Qurolli Kuchlar Akademiyasi
N.S.Abdullayeva – p.f.b. PhD, NamDU, Namangan, O'zbekiston
A.G.Turg'unboyeva – p.f.b. PhD, NamDPI, Namangan, O'zbekiston
M.A.Abdullayeva – professor, NamDU, Namangan, O'zbekiston
I.O.Ergashev – iqt.f.b. PhD, Fiskal instituti, Toshkent, O'zbekiston
N.T.Mamatxanova – p.f.b. PhD, NamDPI, Namangan, O'zbekiston
U.Yu.Axundjanov – t.f.b. PhD, TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston
O.M.Ergashev – t.f.b. PhD, TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston
N.R.Xallieva – iqt.f.b. PhD, Buxoro MTI, Buxoro, O'zbekiston
F.K.Achilova – iqt.f.n., TATU Qarchi filiali, Qarchi, O'zbekiston
A.K.Samyayev – g.f.b. PhD, Sam. vil. ped. mah. mar, Samarqand, O'zbekiston
J.S.Abdullayev – f.-m.f.n., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.
N.D.Botirova – ped.f.b. PhD, TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston

Bug‘doyda sariq zang kasalligini bashorat qilish va nazorat qilish usullari

Mambetnazarov Asan Bisenbayevich, Rasulova Madina Shuxratovna

O‘simliklar karantini va himoyasi ilmiy-tadqiqot instituti

Copyright: © 2025 by the author.

Licensee: This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

Annotatsiya. Sariq zang kasalligi (*Puccinia striiformis f. sp. tritici*) bug‘doy ekinlariga jiddiy tahdid soluvchi global muammolardan biridir. Ushbu maqola kasallikning tarqalishini bashorat qilish usullari va uni nazorat qilish strategiyalarini o‘rganadi. Iqlim sharoitlari, bug‘doy navlari va genetik xususiyatlar kasallik rivojiga ta‘sir etuvchi asosiy omillar sifatida ko‘rib chiqiladi. Tadqiqotda meteorologik ma‘lumotlar, matematik modellar va laboratoriya tahlillari asosida prognoz qilish usullari tahlil qilinadi. Maqola kasallikka qarshi samarali chora-tadbirlar va uni oldini olish bo‘yicha zamonaviy yondashuvlarni muhokama qiladi.

Kalit so‘zlar: bug‘doy, sariq zang, *Puccinia striiformis*, prognoz, iqlim, genetik chidamlilik, fungitsidlar, agrotexnika.

Методы прогнозирования и борьбы с желтой ржавчиной пшеницы

Мамбетназаров Асан Бисенбаевич, Расулова Мадина Шухратовна

НИИ карантина и защиты растений

Аннотация. Желтая ржавчина (*Puccinia striiformis f. sp. tritici*) является одной из глобальных проблем, которая серьезно угрожает посевам пшеницы. В статье изучаются методы прогнозирования распространения заболевания и стратегии борьбы с ним. Климатические условия, сорта пшеницы и генетические особенности рассматриваются как основные факторы, влияющие на развитие заболевания. В исследовании анализируются методы прогнозирования, основанные на метеорологических данных, математических моделях и лабораторных анализах. В статье обсуждаются эффективные меры борьбы с болезнью и современные подходы к ее профилактике.

Ключевые слова: пшеница, желтая ржавчина, *Puccinia striiformis*, прогноз, климат, генетическая устойчивость, фунгициды, агротехника.

Methods of forecasting and combating yellow rust of wheat

Mambetnazarov Asan Bisenbaevich, Rasulova Madina Shukhratovna

Research Institute of Quarantine and Plant Protection

Abstract. Yellow rust disease (*Puccinia striiformis f. sp. tritici*) is one of the global problems that seriously threatens wheat crops. This article studies methods for predicting the spread of the disease and strategies for its control. Climatic conditions, wheat varieties and genetic characteristics are considered as the main factors affecting the development of the disease. The study analyzes forecasting methods based on meteorological data, mathematical models and laboratory analyses. The article discusses effective measures against the disease and modern approaches to its prevention.

Keywords: wheat, yellow rust, *Puccinia striiformis*, forecast, climate, genetic resistance, fungicides, agrotechnics.

Kirish.

Bug‘doy dunyodagi eng muhim oziq-ovqat ekinlaridan biri sifatida millionlab odamlar uchun asosiy oziq-ovqat manbai hisoblanadi. Biroq, sariq zang kasalligi (*Puccinia striiformis f. sp. tritici*) uning hosildorligiga sezilarli darajada zarar yetkazadi. Ushbu zamburug‘iy kasallik barglarda sariq rangli zang dog‘lari hosil qiladi, fotosintez jarayonini buzadi va hosilni kamaytiradi. O‘zbekiston kabi qishloq xo‘jaligi rivojlangan mamlakatlarda kasallikning tarqalishini oldindan bashorat qilish va nazorat qilish choralari muhim ahamiyatga ega. Maqolada sariq zang kasalligining xususiyatlari, prognoz usullari va uni boshqarish strategiyalari o‘rganiladi.

Sariq zang kasalligining xususiyatlari. Sariq zang kasalligi *Puccinia triiformis* zamburug‘i tomonidan qo‘zg‘atiladi va bug‘doyning vegetatsiya davrida katta zarar keltiradi. Kasallik don to‘lish davrida 5-35% hosil yo‘qotishiga, bayroq barg chiqarish bosqichida esa 50-60% zararlanganda hosilning 45-50% gacha kamayishiga olib keladi. Sporalar 0°C dan boshlab rivojlana boshlaydi, lekin 12-23°C harorat oralig‘i uning tarqalishi uchun eng qulay hisoblanadi. Kasallik belgilari dastlab barglarda uzun, sariq dog‘lar shaklida paydo bo‘lib, keyinchalik butun barg yuzasini qoplaydi, bu esa ozuqa moddalari hosil bo‘lishini pasaytiradi.

Sariq zang tropik va subtropik iqlimlarda keng tarqalgan bo‘lib, nam va iliq sharoitlarda tez rivojlanadi. Kasallikning tarqalishi Yaqin Sharq va Janubi-Sharqiy Osiyodan boshlangan deb taxmin qilinsa-da, hozirda Shimoliy Amerika va Yevropa kabi hududlarda ham muammo sifatida davom etmoqda.

Adabiyotlar tahlili va tadqiqot metodologiyasi.

O‘zbekistonda sariq zang kasalligini o‘rganish 1980-yillardan boshlangan bo‘lib, S. Xo‘jaev (1995) va N. Abdullayev (2012) kabi olimlarning tadqiqotlari

muhim hissa qo'shgan [1, 2]. Xo'jaev kasallikni prognoz qilishda iqlim omillarining rolini ta'kidlab, harorat va namlikning ta'sirini o'rgangan. Abdullayev esa meteorologik tahlil, statistik usullar va matematik modellashtirishni qo'llagan holda kasallik tarqalishini bashorat qilish metodlarini taklif qilgan [2].

Tadqiqot metodologiyasi quyidagi yondashuvlarni o'z ichiga oladi:

Meteorologik tahlil: Harorat, namlik va yog'ingarchilik kabi iqlim omillari kasallik rivojiga qanday ta'sir qilishi o'rganiladi.

Statistik modellar: O'tmishdagi kasallik ma'lumotlari asosida kelajakdagi tarqalishni bashorat qilish.

Matematik modellashtirish: Kompyuter modellaridan foydalanib, turli sharoitlarda kasallikning tarqalish tezligini aniqlash.

Laboratoriya tadqiqotlari: Fungitsidlarning samaradorligi va genetik chidamli navlarning xususiyatlari sinovdan o'tkaziladi.

Xorijiy adabiyotlarda, masalan, Kaldal (2018) va FAO (2016) tadqiqotlarida iqlim o'zgarishi va biotexnologiyaning kasallikni nazorat qilishdagi ahamiyati ta'kidlanadi [3, 4].

Prognoz qilish usullari

Sariq zang kasalligini bashorat qilishda quyidagi usullar qo'llaniladi:

Iqlim monitoringi: Yuqori namlik va 12-23°C harorat kasallik tarqalishini tezlashtiradi. Meteorologik ma'lumotlar ushbu sharoitlarni aniqlashda asosiy vosita hisoblanadi.

Vegetatsiya bosqichlarini kuzatish: Bug'doyning o'sish davrlari, ayniqsa bahor va kuzda ekilgan ekinlarning zararlanish darajasi monitoring qilinadi.

Genetik tahlil: Kasallikka chidamli navlarni aniqlash va ishlab chiqish uchun laboratoriya sinovlari o'tkaziladi.

Kompyuter modellari: Iqlim va ekin ma'lumotlari asosida kasallikning potentsial tarqalish hududlari modellashtiriladi.

Natijalar va muhokama

Tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatadiki, iqlim sharoitlari (ayniqsa, harorat va namlik) sariq zang kasalligining tarqalishida hal qiluvchi rol o'ynaydi. Kompyuter modellaridan foydalanish prognozni aniqlashtiradi va fermerlar uchun o'z vaqtida chora ko'rish imkonini beradi. Genetik jihatdan chidamli navlar ishlab chiqish kasallikni cheklashda muhim yutuq bo'lib, hosilni 5-10% gacha oshirishi mumkin. Biroq, fungitsidlarning haddan tashqari qo'llanilishi ekologik xavf tug'dirishi ehtimoli mavjud.

N. Abdullayevning xulosalariga ko'ra, optimal iqlim sharoitlari mavjud bo'lgan hududlarda kasallik tez tarqaladi, bu esa monitoring va prognozning dolzarbligini

oshiradi [2]. Global iqlim o'zgarishi sharoitida kasallikning tarqalish tezligi yanada kuchayishi mumkin.

Kasallikni nazorat qilish choralari

Chidamli navlar: Sariq zangga qarshi genetik chidamlilikka ega bug'doy navlari ekish kasallikni kamaytirishning eng samarali usullaridan biridir.

Fungitsidlar: Kimyoviy vositalar prognoz asosida vaqtida qo'llanilganda samarali bo'ladi, lekin ehtiyotkorlik bilan ishlatilishi lozim.

Agrotexnik tadbirlar: Sug'orish rejimini optimallashtirish va ekin almashlab ekish kasallik xavfini pasaytiradi.

Xulosa.

Bug'doyda sariq zang kasalligini bashorat qilish va nazorat qilish zamonaviy ilmiy yondashuvlarni talab qiladi. Iqlim monitoringi, genetik tadqiqotlar va kompyuter modellaridan foydalanish kasallik tarqalishini oldindan aniqlashda muhim ahamiyatga ega. O'zbekistonda ushbu kasallikka qarshi kurashda chidamli navlar ekish va fungitsidlarni oqilona qo'llash orqali hosilni saqlab qolish mumkin. Kelgusida iqlim o'zgarishlari ta'sirini chuqurroq o'rganish va innovatsion texnologiyalarni joriy etish tavsiya etiladi.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar:

1. S. Xo'jaev. Bug'doyda sariq zang kasalligi va unga qarshi kurash usullari. Toshkent: O'zbekiston qishloq xo'jaligi nashriyoti, 1995, 45-60 betlar.
2. N. Abdullayev. Sariq zang kasalligining tarqalishi va uning prognozlash metodlari. Toshkent: O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi nashriyoti, 2012, 120-130 betlar.
3. Kaldal, K., Nilsson, H., & Johansson, M. (2018). Climate change impact on wheat yellow rust development: A modeling approach. *Agricultural Systems*, 157, 52-59.
4. FAO (2016). Global impact of yellow rust on wheat production. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations.

Jurnal haqida

“Tadqiq va tadbiq” ilmiy-uslubiy jurnali Fer-Teach MChJ tomonidan tashkil etilgan. Mazkur jurnal O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Administratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan 2023 yil 3 mayda №078777 raqam bilan ro‘yxatga olingan.

ISSN 3030-3362

Jurnalda texnologiya sohasidagi ixtisoslashtirilgan jurnal bo‘lib, texnik fanlarning turli sohalari: fizika, matematika, axborot texnologiyalari bo‘yicha tadqiqot va ishlanmalarning barcha asosiy yo‘nalishlarini qamrab oladi. Jurnalda tilshunoslik, o‘qitish metodikasi va texnika fanlarining rivojlanish tarixiga oid ilmiy maqolalar ham chop etiladi.

Manzil: 15010, Farg‘ona viloyati, Farg‘ona shahri, ko‘ch. Solima, 23/4, kvartira. 26

E-mail: chief_editor@rai-journal.uz

Veb-sayt: <https://rai-journal.uz/>

Tillar: o‘zbek, rus, ingliz, qoraqalpoq

О журнале

Научно-методический журнал «Исследования и внедрение» учрежден ООО «FerTeach». Данный журнал зарегистрирован номером № 078777 Агентством информации и массовых коммуникаций при Администрации Президента Республики Узбекистан от 3 мая 2023 года.

ISSN 3030-3362

«Исследования и внедрение» является специализированным журналом в области технологий и охватывает все основные направления исследований и разработок в различных областях технических наук: физика, математика, информационные технологии. Журнал также публикует научные статьи по языкознанию, методике преподавания и истории развития технических наук.

Адрес: 150100, Ферганская область, г. Фергана, ул. Солима, 23/4, кв. 26

E-mail: chief_editor@rai-journal.uz

Сайт: <https://rai-journal.uz/>

Языки: узбекский, русский, английский, каракалпакский

About the journal

The scientific and methodological journal "Research and Implementation" was founded by Fer-Teach LLC. This journal is registered under number 078777 by the Agency for Information and Mass Communications under the Administration of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 3, 2023.

ISSN 3030-3362

"Research and Implementation" is a specialized journal in the field of technology and covers all the main areas of research and development in various fields of technical sciences: physics, mathematics, information technology. The journal also publishes scientific articles on linguistics, teaching methods and the history of the development of technical sciences.

Address: 150100, Fergana region, Fergana city, Solima street, 23/4, apt. 26

E-mail: chief_editor@rai-journal.uz

Website: <https://rai-journal.uz/>

Languages: Uzbek, Russian, English, Karakalpak

DIQQAT!

Jurnal materiallaridan foydalanganda manbani ko'rsatish kerak.

Maqola mualliflari maqolalar mazmuni va ularning nashr etilishi fakti uchun javobgardirlar.

Har doim ham mualliflarning fikrlari tahririyat nuqtai nazarini ifodalamaydi va nashr etilgan ma'lumotlarning haqiqiyliги uchun javobgar emas.

Jurnal tahririyati mualliflar va/yoki uchinchi shaxslar va tashkilotlarga maqolaning e'lon qilinishi natijasida yetkazilishi mumkin bo'lgan zarar uchun javobgar emas.

ВНИМАНИЕ!

При использовании материалов журнала необходимо указывать источник. Авторы статей несут ответственность за содержание статей и за сам факт их публикации.

Редакция не всегда разделяет мнения авторов и не несет ответственности за недостоверность публикуемых данных.

Редакция журнала не несет никакой ответственности перед авторами и/или третьими лицами и организациями за возможный ущерб, вызванный публикацией статьи.

ATTENTION!

When using journal materials, you must indicate the source.

The authors of the articles are responsible for the content of the articles and for the very fact of their publication.

The editors do not always share the opinions of the authors and are not responsible for the unreliability of the published data.

The editorial board of the journal does not bear any responsibility to the authors and / or third parties and organizations for possible damage caused by the publication of the article
